

1 **Title:** Genetic divergence in the natural regeneration of black poplar along the Vistula River in
2 Poland

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7 **Keywords:** *Populus nigra*, genetic variation, natural regeneration, vegetative and generative
8 reproduction, clones, Vistula River

9

10 **Abstract:** Many years of land use transformation within river valleys have drastically changed
11 these ecosystems. Black poplar is a tree species characteristic of riparian habitats.
12 Unfortunately, due to specific environmental requirements, its populations have difficulties
13 with natural regeneration. Here, we genotyped 623 black poplar individuals from four
14 populations located along different sections of the Vistula River. This river, which is the largest
15 in Poland, is characterized by the variable degrees of regulation and transformation of its natural
16 environment. Each black poplar population consisted of a group of mature trees and a group of
17 naturally regenerated trees. The results showed that fully generative regeneration occurred only
18 along the least transformed middle section of the river. One example of regeneration comprised
19 only root suckers, and the remaining two appeared to be half generative and half vegetative in
20 origin. The genetic differentiation among the natural regeneration groups was almost twice as
21 high as that among the mature tree groups. It can be assumed that due to the lack of suitable
22 areas for seed germination, black poplar will reproduce mainly vegetatively, which may be a
23 way to ensure the survival of the species. However, the adaptive potential of the youngest
24 generations is unknown, especially in the face of progressive climate change. Our research
25 confirms the need to monitor seedlings and saplings along major rivers and to conduct
26 molecular analyses to assess their gene pools. We conclude that to preserve black poplar genetic
27 resources, ex situ protection in the form of local clone archives is necessary.

28 **1. Introduction**

29 It is assumed that as climate change progresses, many species, due to various limitations, will
30 lose habitat areas that are optimal for their growth and development. The most dire situation is
31 projected for species that will be unable to compensate for the shifts in their range due to an
32 inability to colonize new areas (Dyderski et al. 2018; Puchałka et al. 2023). Dyderski et al.
33 (2018) showed that among forest trees, the most endangered species are mainly pioneer and
34 coniferous species. Pioneer species have a better ability to spread, and in their case, the threat

35 greater than dispersal limitations would be the lack of areas suitable for colonization (Dyderski
36 et al. 2018). Black poplar is a species that has already experienced negative effects from human
37 activity and, in part, from climate change. It is the main forest tree species of riparian woodlands
38 that are considered centres of biodiversity (Pielech 2021; Rajpar, Rajpar, and Zakaria 2022).
39 Unfortunately, it is estimated that only 1% of the riparian forests that once existed in Europe
40 have remained (Lefèvre et al. 1998; Smulders et al. 2008). Black poplar still occurs throughout
41 Europe, Central Asia, North Africa, and Western Siberia (Bugala 1973). Nevertheless, the
42 number of trees is rapidly decreasing, especially in Western Europe (Cottrell 2004; Holub and
43 Procházka 2000; Lefèvre et al. 1998; Tylkowski 2010). Because there is a real problem with
44 natural regeneration, the population remnants consist mostly of trees that are close to terminal
45 age.

46 Black poplar has great ecological and economic value. It establishes on riverbanks, providing
47 natural flood protection and contributing to substantial improvements in the environment due
48 to its ability to absorb pollutants (Šiler, Skorić, and Mišić 2014). As a fast-growing tree, it is
49 not only an excellent source of biomass for energy uses but also an intermediate product for the
50 furniture and paper industries. Black poplar has been widely used in selective breeding for the
51 development of resilient, fast-growing poplar hybrids (Šiler et al. 2014; Vanden Broeck et al.
52 2005). As a pioneer species, black poplar plays an important role in the initial successional
53 stage of riparian ecosystems (Chenault et al. 2011; Rotach 2004). It is dioecious and reproduces
54 mainly generatively. Mature trees produce large amounts of seeds, but their lifespan under
55 natural conditions is quite short (Braatne, Rood, and Heilman 1996; Vanden Broeck et al. 2005).
56 The light pappus of black poplar seeds promotes long-distance dispersal by wind and water.
57 Specific water and soil conditions, such as bare, moist and permeable soil, and a lack of
58 competition are necessary for the seeds to germinate, but even when this happens, most will not
59 survive the first year due to flooding or drought stress (Johnson 2000; Seiwa et al. 2008; Vanden

60 Broeck et al. 2005). Seedling density can vary from only 20 to, under favourable conditions,
61 more than 4,000 per square metre (Braatne et al. 1996). However, due to environmental
62 restrictions, seedling establishment is very rare, occurring on average every 10–20 years
63 (Vanden Broeck et al. 2005). Moreover, human interference has unfortunately led to a lack of
64 habitat areas that provide proper conditions for seed germination.

65 Under unfavourable environmental conditions, as an alternative reproductive strategy, black
66 poplar can reproduce vegetatively (Braatne et al. 1996). First, branches and twigs that are
67 broken during storms and floods are transported along the river and can then be buried in the
68 sediment, where they can resprout (Braatne et al. 1996; Smulders et al. 2008). Second, damage
69 to the apical meristem can lead to the growth of multiple trunks of the same genotype (Barsoum,
70 Muller, and Skot 2004; Del Tredici 2001; Żukowska, Wójkiewicz, and Lewandowski 2021).
71 Moreover, the root system can produce shoots known as root suckers. Trunk damage or root
72 disturbance due to fire, mowing or grazing promotes the development of root suckers; therefore,
73 we can presume that a stimulus is needed (Barsoum et al. 2004). Apart from the danger posed
74 by the limited possibility of generative reproduction, an additional threat to black poplar is that
75 it may cross with fast-growing hybrid poplar varieties that have been planted in great numbers
76 throughout Europe since the end of the 18th century (Bugala 1973; Vanden Broeck et al. 2005).
77 This poses a real risk to the integrity of the black poplar gene pool (Vanden Broeck et al. 2015).
78 High morphological similarity makes it difficult to distinguish pure black poplars from hybrids
79 based solely on phenotypic characteristics (Bugala 1973).

80 The black poplar is a noteworthy research object because, on the one hand, it has two different
81 reproductive strategies, and on the other hand, its natural ecological niche has clearly been
82 transformed. Furthermore, dioecious species such as black poplar might be particularly
83 susceptible to climate change due to their tendency to spatially segregate male and female
84 individuals. This segregation is often reinforced by physiological and morphological

85 specializations of each sex to distinct microhabitats (Hultine et al. 2016). Therefore, the
86 question arises whether black poplar will be able to survive and maintain genetic variability as
87 well as adaptive potential in the future or whether any actions should be taken to protect this
88 species and its gene pool. In Poland, black poplar is still common, but it should be noted that
89 many populations are rather old and small and occur in the form of small groupings. The
90 remaining river where there are suitable conditions for natural regeneration is the Vistula River
91 (Wójkiewicz et al. 2019), the largest river in Poland, with a length of ca. 1,047 km. The
92 environmental conditions and plant communities along individual river sections vary due to
93 river waterflow regulation works carried out in recent centuries. The waterflow of the upper
94 section has been regulated by approximately 60% (Wójkiewicz et al. 2019; Żelazo 2013).
95 Intensive work on regulating this part of the Vistula began after 1840. The riverbed was
96 subjected to numerous modifications, which resulted in its rapid deepening and narrowing. This
97 led to sedimentation of debris in the spaces between the transverse dams and in the floodplain.
98 Rich sediments that accumulated in floodplains quickly became overgrown with vegetation,
99 leading to a drastic reduction in the capacity of these places. After 1950, the debris was retained
100 by built retention reservoirs, leading to the stabilization of the bed (Żelaziński 2014). The
101 middle section is the least transformed and the most natural, having the greatest ecological
102 value. Plans for regulating the waterflow of the middle Vistula, developed at the end of the 19th
103 century, were partially implemented only after 1945. Cascading, planned in the 1970s, was
104 completely abandoned (Łajczak et al. 2021). The lower and longest section has numerous
105 regulatory structures and levees (Wójkiewicz et al. 2019; Żelazo 2013). On the basis of the
106 degree of transformations, it can be divided into four subsections, which are partially or
107 completely regulated. Regulatory work on the lower Vistula began in 1835–1855. Such
108 waterflow regulation works contributed to the transformation of the riverbed from a braided

109 bed with numerous sandbanks and tussocks into an almost rectilinear type of riverbed with an
110 alternating arrangement of sloping sandbars (Łajczak et al. 2021).

111 Natural regeneration capacity and genetic variation in black poplar are very important issues,
112 considering the progressive nature of climate change, as well as the differential levels of
113 transformation of the Vistula. Therefore, we analysed the gene pools of the remaining black
114 poplar populations where both mature trees and natural regeneration occurred. Specifically, we
115 wanted to answer the following questions: (1) Does the natural regeneration gene pool mirror
116 the gene pool of mature trees? (2) Does the chosen reproductive strategy vary depending on the
117 location and the degree of land transformation? (3) Do populations located in different sections
118 of the Vistula River differ genetically? (4) Are the gene pools of the populations in need of
119 protection, and if so, how should such protection be carried out?

120 **2. Methods**

121 **2.1 Study sites and plant material**

122 We sampled four populations of black poplar trees located along different parts of the Vistula
123 River (Table 1). From each site, we analysed the group of mature trees and the group of
124 naturally regenerated trees (623 individuals in total). We collected fresh leaves that were stored
125 at -20°C until extraction. Most groups of naturally regenerated trees (Vi2R–Vi4R) were
126 collected along a one-metre transect. However, the Vi1R group was collected along a five-
127 metre transect due to the large size of the analysed area. The Vi1 population is located in the
128 upper Vistula section. The entire area is covered with grass and small shrubs. Regarding the
129 Vi2 population from the middle, least regulated section of the Vistula, this area is exposed,
130 sandy, and lacking in grass cover. The Vi3 population is located partly in a nature reserve. The
131 area where the mature tree group is located is overgrown, while the natural regeneration group
132 is located slightly farther away, next to the railway bridge in an open sandy area. The Vi3 and

133 Vi4 populations are located in the regulated section of the Vistula River. Comprehensive full
134 regulation of this section of the riverbed was carried out in the years 1880–1892 after a series
135 of great floods. The riverbed was straightened and narrowed with stone spurs. There is an
136 almost straight-line bed in this part of the river, with a winding current at low water levels and
137 an alternating system of sloping bars and stream pools (Łajczak et al. 2021).

138 Additionally, samples of various poplar varieties were included in the present research as a
139 reference to identify potential hybrids in our dataset. They comprised five individuals marked
140 as *Populus deltoides* trees, 11 male *Populus nigra* cv. *Italica* trees and European hybrids such
141 as *Populus* ‘Grandis’, *P.* ‘Marilandica’, *P.* ‘Robusta’, and *P.* ‘Serotina’. These are the most
142 popular Euramerican hybrids planted in Poland. We also genotyped several hybrid individuals
143 that grew near the black poplar populations we analysed.

144 **2.2 Molecular analyses**

145 Total DNA was extracted from frozen leaves according to a modified cetyl-
146 trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) isolation method (Dumolin, Demesure, and Petit 1995).
147 We used 100 to 120 mg of leaf tissue ground in liquid nitrogen. Five microlitres of RNase A
148 (10 mg/mL) was added after the initial incubation to remove the RNA. Qualitative and
149 quantitative assessment of the isolated DNA was performed using a BioPhotometer plus
150 spectrophotometer (Eppendorf AG, Germany) as well as via agarose electrophoresis.
151 Genotyping of the examined individuals was carried out using 15 microsatellite markers
152 developed by van der Schoot et al. (2000) and Smulders et al. (2001). The amplification of the
153 WPMS markers 01, 03, 04, 07, 10-18, 20 and 22 was performed via three multiplex PCRs
154 according to the protocols described by Wójkiewicz et al. (2019). The size of the PCR products
155 was analysed using fluorescence detection in an ABI3130xl automatic capillary sequencer with
156 GeneScan™ 500 LIZ™ (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) as an internal standard. The
157 genotypes were scored using GeneMapper ver. 4.0 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and

158 confirmed manually. Nuclear DNA *win3* and chloroplast DNA *trnS-trnfM* markers were used
159 to screen hybrid individuals, and the reaction conditions were the same as those described by
160 Wójkiewicz et al. (2019). The identification of hybrid trees was also carried out on the basis of
161 the microsatellite marker data. To identify signals of introgression in the analysed groups of
162 black poplar individuals, the STRUCTURE 2.3.4 program was used (Falush, Stephens, and
163 Pritchard 2003; Pritchard, Stephens, and Donnelly 2000). Ten independent runs were
164 performed for each K from one to 14 with burn-in lengths of 50,000 and 500,00 iterations. We
165 also used GenAlEx ver. 6.5 software to identify clones (Peakall and Smouse 2006, 2012). All
166 hybrid individuals and clones were excluded from further analyses.

167 **2.3 Data analyses**

168 To estimate the frequency of null alleles at all loci, we used the maximum likelihood method
169 (Dempster, Laird, and Rubin 1977), available in the FreeNA program (Chapuis and Estoup
170 2007). The parameters of genetic variability were determined by calculating parameters such
171 as the mean number of alleles (A), mean effective number of alleles (A_E), number of private
172 alleles (A_P), and the mean observed (H_O) and expected heterozygosity (H_E). These parameters
173 were calculated for each of the analysed groups using GenAlEx ver. 6.5 software. The FSTAT
174 ver. 2.9.4. program (Goudet 2003) was used to determine allelic richness (A_R). The values of
175 the inbreeding coefficient were determined, including null allele correction (F_{ISNull}), using
176 INEst ver. 2.2 software (Chybicki and Burczyk 2009). The calculations were performed using
177 two models – the 'nfb' model, which considers null alleles, inbreeding coefficients and
178 genotyping failures – and the 'nb' model, which considers null alleles and genotyping failures.
179 A comparison between these two models allowed us to determine the importance of inbreeding.
180 We set the parameters as follows: 200,000 MCMC iterations, updates performed every 10th
181 cycle, and a burn-in of 20,000. To determine the level of genetic variability within and among
182 the analysed populations, we applied the analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) method,

183 with a p value calculated with 10,000 permutations, implemented in Arlequin ver. 3.5.2.2
184 (Excoffier and Lischer 2010). We also calculated population pairwise fixation indices (F_{ST}) and
185 Slatkin's analogues of F_{ST} (R_{ST}). We performed the principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) using
186 GenAlEx to assess the genetic relationships among the populations. To assign the studied black
187 poplar individuals to a given genetic group, we conducted a clustering analysis in the
188 STRUCTURE program. The calculation parameters were the same as those described in section
189 2.2. We used StructureSelector web-based software (Li and Liu 2018) to generate the results.
190 Because there were large differences in the number of individuals among the groups, the most
191 likely value of K was determined using the Evanno method (Evanno, Regnaut, and Goudet
192 2005) and the Puechmaille method (Puechmaille 2016). To estimate the effective size of
193 individual populations (N_e) with the linkage disequilibrium (LD) approach (Waples and
194 England 2011), we used the NeEstimator ver. 2.01 program (Do et al. 2014). We followed the
195 authors' recommendation and set the allele frequency threshold (P_{crit}) to 0.02. The 95%
196 confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated using the parametric option that implements the χ^2
197 approximation (Waples 2005). In the last step, we used two bottleneck testing approaches.
198 Using the INEst program, the M-ratio (MR), defined as the ratio of the number of alleles to the
199 range of allele sizes, was calculated (Garza and Williamson 2001). We also performed a test
200 for excess heterozygosity (Cornuet and Luikart 1996) with the parameters described by Peery
201 et al. (2012). The analysis was carried out under the two-phase mutation model (TPM), which
202 includes single-step and multistep mutations. For both bottleneck tests, significance was
203 analysed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test based on 1,000,000 permutations.

204 **3. Results**

205 **3.1 Identification of hybrids and clones**

206 In the analysed populations, we detected a total of 258 clones, which constituted 41.41% of all
207 individuals (Table 2). We recorded high clonality in the Vi3R, Vi4M, and Vi4R groups

208 (74.57%, 75.61, and 93.59%, respectively). We did not find any clones in the Vi2R group. Since
209 the Vi4R group contained only clones, this group was excluded from further analyses. We
210 detected one hybrid individual in the Vi4M group, which was a cross between pure *P. nigra*
211 and the hybrid *P. 'Grandis'*.

212 **3.2 Parameters of genetic variation and demographic history**

213 The frequency of null alleles was high at the WPMS08 locus; therefore, this locus was excluded
214 from further analyses. The genetic variability parameters estimated for the individual groups
215 are listed in Table 2. Both the number of alleles and the number of effective alleles were
216 comparable between the analysed groups, with $A = 9.686$ and $A_E = 5.338$ on average. The
217 highest values of both parameters were recorded in the Vi2R group and then in the Vi2M group
218 from the middle Vistula section. The mean allelic richness was $A_R = 6.695$ and was similar
219 between groups, with the highest values recorded for the Vi2R and Vi2M groups and the lowest
220 for the Vi1R and Vi1M groups. The number of private alleles was very high in the Vi2R group
221 ($A_P = 27$), while it was markedly lower in the remaining groups (average $A_P = 2$). Nevertheless,
222 there were differences in allele frequencies at various loci between individual
223 populations/groups. The observed and expected heterozygosity were high and comparable
224 between the analysed groups (average $H_O = 0.754$, average $H_E = 0.749$). Inbreeding was, in
225 almost every case, insignificant. According to the results of the INEst program, the 'nfb'
226 inbreeding model was better only for the Vi2R group – inbreeding was the significant
227 component of the model but still at a low level of less than 2% ($F_{ISnull} = 0.019$). For the effective
228 population size, high values were detected only in the Vi2 population ($N_e = 140.40$ in Vi2M
229 and $N_e = 233.00$ in Vi2R); in the remaining groups, these values were much lower ($N_e = 16.10$ -
230 38.80). The results showed that all groups went through a bottleneck at a more distant time in
231 the past. In most cases, the bottleneck effect was significant at $p = 0.001$, but only in the case

232 of the Vi2M group at $p = 0.05$. We detected no recent bottlenecks in any of the analysed groups,
233 as the p values were not significant for the heterozygosity excess test.

234 **3.3 Genetic differentiation and clustering of gene pools**

235 The AMOVA revealed that the genetic differentiation among the studied groups of naturally
236 regenerated trees was almost twice as high ($F_{ST} = 0.0616$; $R_{ST} = 0.0707$) as that within the group
237 of mature trees ($F_{ST} = 0.0307$; $R_{ST} = 0.0397$) (Table 3). The pairwise F_{ST} and R_{ST} values between
238 each group are presented in Table 4. The greatest similarity was found between the Vi2M and
239 Vi2R groups, while the Vi1M and Vi1R groups exhibited the greatest difference. The PCoA
240 results showed that the Vi4M group was very different from the other populations. The greatest
241 difference was observed between the Vi4M and Vi1R groups (Fig. 1A.). At the individual tree
242 level, we observed that the gene pool of natural regeneration differed from the gene pool of
243 mature trees in the Vi1 population (Fig. 1B.), with the difference being smaller than that of the
244 Vi3 population (Fig. 1D.), and was not different in the Vi2 population (Fig. 1C.). According to
245 the Evanno method, two genetic groups ($K = 2$) represented the most likely genetic structure of
246 the analysed individuals. In this case, the Vi1 population constituted a separate genetic group.
247 Using the Puechmaille method, the most likely number of clusters was $K = 3$, where the Vi1
248 and Vi3 populations formed distinct subgroups.

249 **4. Discussion**

250 **4.1 Hybrids and clones**

251 It can be difficult to distinguish hybrid individuals from pure black poplar species based solely
252 on phenotypic characteristics (Bugala 1973). Using molecular tools, we identified one hybrid
253 individual among mature trees of the Vi4M group, which we recognized as a cross between
254 pure *P. nigra* and the hybrid *P. 'Grandis'*. Since the *P. 'Grandis'* variety is female, the identified
255 hybrid resulted from pollination of the female *P. 'Grandis'* by the male *P. nigra*. This result is

256 consistent with the concept of preferential hybridization mentioned by Pospíšková and Šálková
257 (2006), whose studies showed that all hybrid seedlings came from one female *P. × canadensis*
258 genotype. Zsuffa, Lin, and Payne (1999) showed that artificial crossings between female *P.*
259 *nigra* and male *P. × canadensis* were unsuccessful and achievable only with the help of embryo
260 culture. In contrast, they found that pollinating female *P. deltoides* with male *P. nigra* pollen
261 was very easy. Vanden Broeck et al. (2004), for the first time and in contrast to previous studies,
262 showed that spontaneous hybridization between female *P. nigra* and male *P. × canadensis* is
263 possible, but only when there is a very small amount of *P. nigra* pollen in the pollen cloud.
264 Such hybrids were present in open-pollinated *P. nigra* females but at a frequency of only 4%
265 (Vanden Broeck et al. 2021). The percentage of hybrids in the Vi4M group in the present study
266 was low (0.51%). Similar to our results, another study revealed that there were no progeny
267 originating from female cultivars of *P. × canadensis* among 154 poplar seedlings that
268 spontaneously colonized the restored habitat along the Common Meuse River in the
269 Netherlands (Vanden Broeck et al. 2021). Other studies revealed higher, though still low, levels
270 of hybridization. Out of 582 analysed poplar individuals, Wójkiewicz et al. (2021) detected 34
271 hybrids (5.84%) that occurred in five of the nine studied populations located along the Odra
272 River in Poland. Bordács et al. (2002) identified 4.3% hybrid offspring in one of the two
273 analysed populations in Hungary. Regarding population Vi2, no hybrid individuals were
274 detected in the examined groups of seedlings in the year of harvest, but it should be emphasized
275 that the presence of hybrid individuals in the natural regeneration of black poplar may vary
276 seasonally. Wójkiewicz et al. (2019) identified three hybrid seedlings in an area near Vi2R.
277 Two of them were classified as the F2 generation, and one was classified as a black poplar
278 backcross. Overall, the risk of gene hybridization depends on many factors, such as geographic
279 location, river area, and pollen and seed variability and abundance. Flowering synchronization,
280 affected by environmental conditions such as temperature and photoperiod, is likely the key

281 factor influencing the intensity and direction of hybridization. It also appears that when there
282 are large natural populations of black poplar, it pollinates preferentially. Conversely, if more
283 hybrids are present, pure black poplars should be reintroduced to reduce the risk of introgression
284 from hybrid varieties (Vanden Broeck et al. 2021).

285 In our study, the highest percentage of clones was observed in the populations from the lower
286 section of the Vistula River, where clones constituted 50% of the Vi3 population and 94.92%
287 of the Vi4 population, and where we discovered only 10 different genotypes. In the population
288 Vi1 from the upper section, clones constituted 20% of all individuals. These two sections of the
289 Vistula River are quite heavily transformed, so the phenomenon of such a high number of clones
290 presumably forming from root suckers is not surprising. We identified clones for 11 genotypes,
291 which were replicated one to 13 times in the Vi3 population, and for five genotypes, which
292 were replicated one to four times in the Vi1 population. The Vi2 population from the middle
293 section of the river, which is the most natural area, had the lowest percentage of clones, at only
294 3.46%. The high number of clones is comparable to previous results of research conducted
295 mostly along rivers with regulated waterflow. Wójkiewicz et al. (2021), who studied nine
296 populations from the heavily transformed Odra River in Poland, found a relatively large
297 proportion of clones ranging from 13% to 48%. Regarding other European countries, Barsoum
298 et al. (2004) and Smulders et al. (2002) reported that 22% and 42% of the genotypes analysed
299 along the Garonne River in France and the Rhine River in the Netherlands, respectively, were
300 repeated in their studies. Furthermore, Smulders et al. (2008) located larger groups of clones
301 along rivers where the level of human activity is high, i.e., along the Rhine River (41%) and
302 along the Usk River in Great Britain (97%), where only two genotypes were discovered. The
303 same research group found lower clonality (13% or less) in populations growing in Italy,
304 Austria, and Germany and no duplicate clones in samples from populations along rivers in
305 Spain, France, the Czech Republic, and Ukraine. Notably, clones were usually the result of two

306 clonal replicates of a single tree. The clones identified by Smulders et al. (2008) were limited
307 to a single local population, except for on the Usk River, where they grew along the entire river
308 as a result of human planting. In our study, the clones, which were located close to each other,
309 were probably formed from root suckers. The areas where we found vegetative regeneration
310 had been transformed in the past and were largely covered with tall grass; therefore, the
311 conditions were not suitable for generative regeneration.

312 **4.2 The divergence of natural regeneration gene pools**

313 The comparisons between mature trees and natural regenerating trees revealed different results.
314 According to the PCoA, the gene pool of Vi2R regeneration most closely reflected the gene
315 pool of mature trees in the same location. Vi1R regeneration, on the other hand, was the most
316 genetically distinct from Vi1M. Partial differentiation was observed for Vi3M vs. Vi3R groups
317 (Fig. 1). Greater differences between the gene pools of older trees and natural regeneration
318 suggest a limited number of parents, especially mother trees. Among the trees classified as
319 Vi1M, there was only one large female tree that could be the mother of most of the Vi1R
320 regeneration. The AMOVA results showed that the genetic differentiation among the groups of
321 naturally regenerated trees was twice as high ($F_{ST} = 0.0616$; $R_{ST} = 0.0707$) as that among the
322 groups of mature trees ($F_{ST} = 0.0307$; $R_{ST} = 0.0397$). These values were significantly greater
323 than those in Polish black poplar populations located in the middle Vistula, where Wójkiewicz
324 et al. (2019) found that $F_{ST} = 0.0037$. Along the short middle section of the river described by
325 the authors, there were no statistically significant differences among populations. Moreover,
326 the differentiation found in our study was even greater than that calculated by Wójkiewicz et
327 al. (2021) for populations growing along the strongly transformed Odra River ($F_{ST} = 0.0443$;
328 $R_{ST} = 0.0527$).

329 When we carefully analysed allele frequencies in all groups, we found that the differences were
330 not only in the pools of private and rare alleles (frequency $\leq 5\%$), which is inevitable but also in

331 the more common alleles. Vi1R regeneration had at least five times lower frequency of six
332 alleles (a drop from 0.111–0.222 to 0.010–0.031). What is more interesting, the frequency of
333 allele 235 in the WPMS20 locus increased from 0.056 to 0.337. This finding confirms our
334 speculation that the oldest female tree in the Vi1M group gave rise to most trees, as no other
335 tree classified as Vi1M had this allele. A similar situation occurred in Vi3, where the frequency
336 of allele 229 in locus WPMS07 increased from 0.015 to 0.100. These results are alarming, as
337 they indicate a situation that may lead to a progressive increase in inbreeding, rendering these
338 naturally regenerated stands more prone to the adverse effects of genetic drift. We can suppose
339 that the adaptive potential of the following generations will also decline.

340 **4.3 Root suckering as an alternative to regeneration from seeds in transformed habitats**

341 Due to late and incomplete work on the regulation of the middle section of the Vistula River,
342 changes in the geometry of the riverbed are not as large as those in the upper section of the river
343 (Łajczak et al. 2021). This most natural part of the river still retains all conditions necessary for
344 seed germination, i.e., sandy terrain and open space that could be periodically flooded. The
345 Vi2R group from this section of the river appears to be the only typical generative regeneration.
346 This regeneration, apart from being the largest, is also the only one in which we did not detect
347 any root suckers. However, young seedlings face survival difficulties. Seedlings are vulnerable
348 to drought until they become saplings with roots that can reach alluvial water tables at depths
349 of two metres or more, which is unattainable in the first growing season (Braatne et al. 1996).
350 Additionally, seedlings are attractive food for animals, especially during winter.

351 The regulation and transformation of river valleys may prevent successful sexual reproduction
352 and seedling recruitment. In the Vi1R group from the upper section of the Vistula, the situation
353 was mixed, partly involving root suckers and partial generative regeneration. Our research also
354 covered two populations located in the lower and longest section of the river with a substantial
355 degree of transformation. In the case of the Vi3R group, the situation was also mixed; most

356 individuals were derived from root suckers, but some of them were produced via generative
357 regeneration. This may be because this group grew next to the railway bridge. During its
358 construction, the area was probably exposed, which meant that the conditions created by the
359 construction work partially enabled the germination of seeds and the survival of seedlings.
360 Regarding the Vi4 population, which is located closest to the influx of Vistula, the trees grew
361 relatively far from the present-day river current. They likely grew there because of the original
362 course of the Vistula River. There is currently no area favourable for seed germination or
363 seedling development, and all the young specimens we found were root suckers. Therefore, it
364 appears that under unfavourable environmental conditions, the only available reproductive
365 strategy is vegetative. Čortan and Tubić (2017), in their work carried out along the upper
366 Danube in Serbia, found that successful regeneration still occurs, but it is sporadic and mainly
367 vegetative. They concluded that 78% of individuals had good or decent regenerative potential,
368 13% had poor regenerative potential, and 10% had no regenerative capacity. The authors
369 emphasized, however, that natural regeneration was mainly vegetative. There was no specific
370 pattern of distribution of individuals with different natural regenerative strategies, and
371 individuals were distributed randomly in the analysed area. No particular environmental
372 conditions directly affected the ability to regenerate, but this issue requires more research on
373 environmental factors and competition with other taxa.

374 **4.4 Genetic variation and differentiation of populations located in different sections of the** 375 **river**

376 Our research showed that the analysed populations are characterized by high genetic diversity,
377 with the Vi2 population having the highest genetic variability, as indicated by the parameters
378 described in Table 2. Genetic diversity parameters such as the number of alleles, the effective
379 number of alleles, and allelic richness were comparable between individual groups of black
380 poplar. These results are in line with other studies on Polish or European populations of black

381 poplar (Čortan et al. 2016; Čortan and Tubić 2017; Pospíšková and Šálková 2006; Wójkiewicz
382 et al. 2021). The number of private alleles was also comparable between individual groups and
383 ranged from zero to six, except for the Vi2R group, where $A_P = 27$. This high A_P value may be
384 because at least some seeds were transported with the river current from different locations.
385 Furthermore, the seedlings grew in two long rows adjacent to the main riverbed, so we can
386 assume that they developed during different periods. Our results are similar to those obtained
387 by Wójkiewicz et al. (2019), where A_P ranged from three to 19, or by Čortan et al. (2016), where
388 A_P ranged from two to 40. The average level of heterozygosity of the analysed groups did not
389 differ from the level of heterozygosity of black poplar populations growing both in Poland
390 (Lewandowski et al. 2021; Lewandowski and Litkowiec 2017; Wójkiewicz et al. 2019, 2021)
391 and in other European countries (Čortan et al. 2016; Jelić et al. 2015; Mazal et al. 2022;
392 Smulders et al. 2008).

393 Despite the uniform level of genetic variation, the pairwise F_{ST} and R_{ST} values showed that the
394 Vi1M, Vi1R, and Vi4M groups were the most genetically different from the others. The results
395 of the PCoA confirmed the above results, as the above-mentioned groups clustered on opposite
396 sites of the first coordinate, which explained 52.08% of the total genetic variation. Genetic
397 clustering revealed that according to the Evanno method, the analysed populations from the
398 Vistula River belonged to two different genetic clusters, where the Vi1 population from the
399 upper section of the river constituted a separate genetic group. Considering the Puechmaille
400 method, which is thought to be more accurate when the studied groups differ in the number of
401 individuals, the most likely genetic structure of the analysed trees was represented by three
402 genetic groups, where the Vi1 and Vi3 populations constituted separate subgroups. This result
403 supports greater genetic structuring of black poplar populations and constraints to gene flow
404 along the Vistula River.

405 **4.5 Conservation implications**

406 Our results indicated that all groups experienced a bottleneck effect in the more distant past; in
407 turn, the insignificance of all p values for the excess heterozygosity test showed that no
408 bottleneck occurred recently in any of the analysed groups. The estimated effective population
409 size was greater only for the mid-river Vi2 population ($N_e = 140.40$ for Vi2M and $N_e = 233.00$
410 for Vi2R). In the remaining groups, the N_e values ranged from 16.10 to 38.80. Franklin (1980)
411 proposed the 50/500 rule, which is an important indicator in conservation genetics. It assumes
412 that populations with N_e less than 50 are at risk of extinction due to reduced survival and
413 reproduction resulting from inbreeding. To ensure long-term viability, the population must have
414 a N_e greater than or equal to 500. Taking the above into account, we can conclude that the low
415 effective sizes of the analysed populations are alarming despite low and, in almost every case,
416 insignificant inbreeding and still high genetic variation.

417 The black poplar populations in Poland are mostly old, close to terminal age, and usually occur
418 in small groups. For example, due to significant transformations of the Warta River, there is no
419 area within its reach that is suitable for seed germination and seedling growth (Lewandowski
420 et al. 2021). Field observations conducted by Żukowska et al. (2021) showed that most
421 individuals along the Odra River are old and that the heavily transformed river valley does not
422 meet the required water and soil conditions for seed germination. For that reason, black poplar
423 also has little chance of generative regeneration along this river. Our research shows that black
424 poplar populations still maintain a high level of genetic variability along the Vistula River. The
425 groups of naturally regenerated trees are more diverse than the group of mature trees, which is
426 a good outcome because it increases diversity. On the other hand, the adaptive potential of
427 natural regeneration in the face of climate change is unknown. Moreover, low N_e values may
428 lead to the extinction of these populations within several generations. It can be said that the
429 Vistula River is the last place for the generative reproduction of black poplar in Poland.
430 Nevertheless, although natural regeneration still occurs, it is not known whether this species

431 will survive. The obtained results indicate that the gene pools are not preserved and are
432 diverging, moving away from the original dynamic. The fate of young individuals cannot be
433 predicted, especially with progressive climatic changes. Root suckers are a kind of lifeline for
434 the survival of this species, but they can have very negative consequences in terms of genetic
435 variation and perhaps adaptive potential. Studies indicate that clonality increases allelic
436 diversity, polymorphism, and heterozygosity in a population but reduces genotypic diversity
437 (Meloni et al. 2013; Żukowska et al. 2021). We conclude that to preserve black poplar gene
438 pools, ex situ protection in the form of local clone archives is needed. This type of protection
439 for the populations from the upper and lower sections of the Vistula River seems to be
440 necessary, and the middle section of the river should be monitored for regeneration and survival
441 of seedlings and saplings.

442 Our research showed that generative regeneration occurs quite rarely. Although natural
443 regeneration still occurs, it is vegetative in most places. Black poplar is a species that requires
444 open space for seed colonization, which is almost impossible in Poland due to the past
445 transformations of river valleys. Natural regeneration may only seem to be generative; to verify
446 this, it is necessary to carry out analyses using molecular biology techniques. Vegetative
447 regeneration may be a way for black poplar to survive, but root suckers usually grow only from
448 a few genotypes, as seen in our studies, where root suckers came from five, 10 or 11 trees.
449 However, the genetic basis for the formation of root suckers and the reasons why some
450 individuals are more predisposed to are unknown, and this topic requires further research.
451 Considering both our research and research previously conducted in Poland, taking action to
452 ensure the protection of black poplar in our country seems to be necessary.

453 Table 1. Description of black poplar populations analysed in the study. *N* – number of individuals

Pop	Group	Study site	River section	Location	<i>N</i>	Age (yrs)
Vi1	Vi1M	Tarnobrzeg, mature trees	upper	N 50.55	14	30-130
	Vi1R	Tarnobrzeg, natural regeneration		E 21.63	56	1-20
Vi2	Vi2M	Wysoczyn, mature trees	middle	N 51.90	61	80-150
	Vi2R	Wysoczyn, natural regeneration		E 21.25	199	1
Vi3	Vi3M	Toruń, mature trees	lower	N 53.00	37	30-150
	Vi3R	Toruń, natural regeneration		E 18.61	59	1-20
Vi4	Vi4M	Mątowy Wielkie, mature trees	lower	N 54.01	41	20-40
	Vi4R	Mątowy Wielkie, natural regeneration		E 18.85	156	1-10

454

455 Table 2. Genetic diversity parameters (average values), where *C* is clonality, *A* is the number of alleles,
 456 *A_E* is the number of effective alleles, *A_R* is the allelic richness, *A_P* is the number of private alleles, *H_O* is
 457 the observed heterozygosity, *H_E* is the expected heterozygosity, *F_{ISnull}* is the mean inbreeding coefficient
 458 corrected for the presence of null alleles (a – inbreeding is the significant component of the model), *Ne*
 459 is the effective population size, MR is the M-ratio (MR significantly < MReq at ****p* < 0.001; ***p* < 0.01;
 460 **p* < 0.05), and MReq are MRs under mutation-drift equilibrium.

	C [%]	A	A_E	A_R	A_P	H_O	H_E	F_{ISnull} 1	Ne	Ne 95% C Is	MR	MReq
Vi1	35.7	5.867	4.18	6.07	0	0.80	0.74	0.00	16.10	9.20-	0.536*	0.717
M	1		2	1		0	9	8		38.10	**	
Vi1	16.0	9.933	3.75	5.22	4	0.75	0.68	0.00	30.10	25.90-	0.595*	0.797
R	7		9	5		1	8	2		35.40	**	
Vi2	12.8	12.46	6.85	7.48	6	0.75	0.78	0.00	140.4	105.40	0.682*	0.783
M	6	7	1	3		4	9	8		0		
Vi2	0	15.20	7.38	7.61	27	0.75	0.79	0.01	233.0	204.00	0.691*	0.833
R		0	4	6		2	8	9 ^a		0	-	
Vi3	10.8	10.00	5.92	7.05	2	0.79	0.79	0.01	38.80	32.00-	0.608*	0.701
M	1	0	1	4		2	2	1		48.30	**	
Vi3	74.5	7.867	4.71	6.76	0	0.72	0.73	0.01	30.30	21.20-	0.600*	0.732
R	7		7	7		1	4	1		49.10	**	
Vi4	75.6	6.467	4.55	6.65	2/	0.71	0.69	0.00	∞	66.70-	0.478	0.663
M	1		4	0		0	3	6		9		
Avg	40.9	9.686	5.33	6.69	5	0.75	0.74	0.01	162.9			
	4		8	5		4	9	0		0		

461 Table 3. Results of the AMOVA of (I) the groups of mature trees Vi1M-4M and (II) the groups of natural
 462 regenerations Vi1R-4R. All values are significant at *p* < 0.001. d.f. – degrees of freedom.

Source of variation		d.f.	F_{ST}	R_{ST}
I	Among populations	3	0.0307	0.0397
	Within populations	204	0.9693	0.9603
II	Among populations	2	0.0616	0.0707
	Within populations	523	0.9384	0.9293

463

464 Table 4. Genetic diversity coefficients among the studied black poplar populations: F_{ST} (below diagonal)
 465 and R_{ST} (above diagonal). Statistically insignificant values are marked in italics ($p > 0.05$).

	Vi1M	Vi1R	Vi2	Vi2R	Vi3	Vi3R	Vi4M
Vi1M		<i>-0.004</i>	0.133	0.119	0.078	0.066	0.129
Vi1R	0.017		0.093	0.085	0.060	0.077	0.096
Vi2M	0.040	0.074		<i>0.001</i>	<i>0.010</i>	0.035	<i>0.010</i>
Vi2R	0.037	0.075	0.004		0.013	0.046	<i>0.025</i>
Vi3M	0.052	0.102	0.021	0.018		<i>0.009</i>	<i>0.005</i>
Vi3R	0.071	0.119	0.032	0.035	<i>0.007</i>		<i>0.019</i>
Vi4M	0.041	0.092	<i>0.002</i>	<i>0.003</i>	<i>0.010</i>	0.042	

466

467 Figure 1. Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) carried out at the (A) population level and (B, C, D)
468 individual level.

469

470 Figure 2. (A) Bar plots showing STRUCTURE results for the two most adequate K values, K=2
 471 (according to the Evanno method) and K=3 (according to the Puechmaille method). (B) Distribution of
 472 delta K over K=1-14 according to the Evanno method. (C) The MedMeanK, MaxMeanK, MedMedK,
 473 and MaxMedK estimators used in the Puechmaille method to determine the most adequate K value.

474

475 **Ethics and Integrity statements:**

476 • **data availability statement**

477 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, D.
478 Robak, upon reasonable request.

479 • **ethics and permit approval statement**

480 The authors declare that they obtained the approval of the Regional Directorate for
481 Environmental Protection for conducting the study in Kępa Bazarowa Nature Reserve in Toruń,
482 Poland.

483 • **funding statement**

484 This research was financially supported by the Polish National Science Centre
485 (2021/41/B/NZ9/00722). Additional support was provided by the Institute of Dendrology,
486 Polish Academy of Sciences.

487 • **conflict of interest disclosure**

488 The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

489 • **permission to reproduce material from other sources**

490 Not applicable.

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